

Eliminating Drug and Substance Use in Kiruhura District for Inclusive Community Health Services and Wellness to Achieve SDG 2030 Agenda in Western Uganda

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Abstract

This paper presents the most urgent need for all Kiruhura district public health stakeholders to unite against controlling the current threatening drug (substance) abuse linked community mental health problems in the western region of Uganda. The main objectives of the paper are to discuss the main causes, sources and users of drugs(substances) by different members of the local communities in the Kiruhura district; discuss the different types of drugs and substances that are commonly used in the different stata of the socio-economic demographics in the district; discuss the effects of the current drug abuse in individuals, families, and local community members, and the mitigation measures and practical solutions that have been attempted to address the problem. This paper was based on the health policy reviews, ministerial political statements to the national parliament (assembly) of Uganda, local government district development plan of (2021/ 2021-2025) Kiruhura district, multiple internet searches by search engines like Google, international reports by WHO, UNICEF, UNPFA, World Bank, EU, UNDP, UNESCO, UNECA, CSOS, public health research findings, good practice, lessons learned, key informants, and media coverage through news bulletins. The findings attested that the common causes and sources of drug and substance abuse in Kiruhura district are mostly: depression, anxiety, schizophrenia, as well as a personality disorder, lack of parental guide and self-imposed boredom (mindlessness or idleness), joblessness (unemployment), and covid-19 lockdown. The types of drugs (substances) used in the district are called: stimulants, opioids, and benzodiazepines, antihistamines, alcohol. These adverse effects of drug (substance) abuse have surfaced in the district: high rate of illicit and prescription drugs misuse (self-medication) among people, lack of adequate data due to very limited research done on drug use, cases of personality disorder epidemic, laziness among many youths, erratic social behaviour, awkward cases of domestic violence including gender-based sexual violence, incidents of drug-related STDs/STI including HIV/AIDS, school dropouts, and high-risk peer pressure (wrong groups) activities. Globally, the use has reached an all-time high. The males (men and boys) are more drug abusers than their female counterparts, the women and girls. In response to the predictably looming social, economic, environmental, and political upheavals (fallouts) of these drug and substance-related mental health epidemic in the area, the district, Uganda government, civil society organizations, education institutions like the universities and schools, faith-based (spiritual) groups, UN agencies, and development partners of the district have moved in to launch and implement public health policies, universal education programmes, gender equality and environment (climate change action plan) community services, employment and voluntary work, family planning initiatives, community tourism with a focus on the Lake Mburo National Game Park (LMNP), operation wealth creation (OWC) for household incomes and socio-economic welfare, anti-narcotics law enforcement, community media led by community radio, turning to Good for spiritual (moral) transformation, community outreach, research projects, savings cooperative groups (SACCOS), and public communication campaigns.

Keywords: Kiruhura district, drug/substance, SDG 2030 Agenda, Covid-19, youth, Uganda